

DELAMINATION FRACTURE TOUGHNESS AND MECHANISMS OF INTERLAYERED BMI COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Delamination fracture of three grades of IM7 fibre/BMI matrix unidirectional composites with different extents of interlayering (0, 15, 30 μm interlayer thicknesses) was studied. Mode I and II fracture energies obtained from DCB and ENF tests were found to increase with the extent of interleaving. Delamination mechanisms of the interlayered materials in mode II fracture were studied through microscopy. The sequence of fracture events was concluded to be as follows: First, a plastic deformation zone formed in the interlayer ahead of the pre-embedded delamination crack, and this was followed by sub-critical delamination growth. Eventually, unstable delamination occurred at interlayer/ply interface and inside the ply.

Keywords: interlaminar fracture, interlayering, fractography, fracture mechanisms.

1. INTRODUCTION

Different fabrication procedures have been devised in recent years to produce composite laminates containing discrete resin layers (*named interlayers herein*) between prepreg plies for enhanced damage tolerance [1,2]. Compression after impact (CAI) and delamination toughness data have been reported in the literature as evaluations of the effectiveness of interlayering. However, to the authors' knowledge, the underlying deformation mechanisms with the presence of the resin interlayers have yet to be established. It appears that along with the conventional damage tolerance data acquisition, detailed fractographic work is in demand to understand the exact role of the interlayer. It is only after the successful completion of such work that the interlayering technologies can be employed effectively.

This paper introduces an experimental study of delamination fracture of three grades of IM7 carbon fiber/BMI matrix composites produced and supplied by The Hexcel Corporation. The systems are identified A, B and C. Grade A is a baseline material in which there is no interlayer. Grades B and C are interlayered, with an average interlayer thicknesses of 15 and 30 μm respectively. The objective of the work reported here is to acquire delamination toughness data and, more importantly, to understand the mechanisms behind the enhancement of damage tolerance with interlayering. Mode I and II delamination test results are reported. However the emphasis is placed on the presentation and analysis of fractographic information. Especially, the path of delamination crack in interlayered materials under mode II loading was analyzed to deduce the mechanisms of fracture. It is hoped that such information will offer reference value to future development of interlayered materials.

2. DELAMINATION FRACTURE TESTS

2.1 Specimen Geometries and Test Procedures

The double cantilever beam (DCB) and end notch flexure (ENF) tests were used to generate mode I and II delamination energy data. The specimens were all 24 ply thick (approximately 3.3 mm for grades A and B, and 3.5 mm for grade C), 25.4 mm wide and 150 mm long. The span for the mode II ENF test was 120 mm. Both types of tests were conducted under displacement control with cross-head rates of 5.08 and 2.54 mm/min for mode I and II tests respectively. The mode II pre-crack procedure [3,4] was followed to eliminate the bluntness caused by a 12.5 μm thick PTFE film embedded as a delamination starter during the stacking-up process. The initial delamination length after such pre-cracking was about 30 mm in both types of specimens.

In the mode I test, repeated loading-unloading was conducted on each specimen and the load-displacement response recorded. Figure 1(a) gives examples of typical results. Extensive fiber bridging was observed in all the three grades of composites during the tests. This bridging effect was reflected by quite severe non-linearity on the load-displacement curve. In the mode II tests, all the specimens failed unstably, as shown by the examples in Figure 1(b). A small extent of non-linearity was discernible on the recorded curves just before the sudden load drop, as commonly found in this type of tests [3].

Figure 1 Typical load-deflection responses of mode I and II delamination tests

Standard data reduction schemes based on beam bending theory were adopted to derive the fracture toughness from the load-displacement response [5].

2.2 Test Results

Figure 2 summarizes the results of the delamination fracture. The CAI strengths of the three grades obtained by the material manufacturer are also plotted as a reference. Two fracture energy values are shown for each mode of fracture. In the mode I case, the initiation value corresponds to the energy of the first delamination propagation after pre-cracking, while the propagation value corresponds to the average of the energies of the incremental delamination with stabilized fiber bridging. In the mode II case, these two were obtained using the maximum linear load and the peak load.

Figure 2. Delamination test results and CAI data

3. MODE II INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE MECHANISM STUDIES

Fractographic studies were carried out on both mode I and II test specimens [5]. However, due to the limitation of space, only that on the mode II fracture specimens are reported.

3.1 Fracture Surface Morphology

As a first step, scanning electron microscopy was conducted to examine the fracture surface morphologies of the specimens of the three grades. Figure 3 presents the typical results. In the interlayered materials, different morphologies were found across the width of the specimens; The majority of the area featured predominantly fiber/matrix interface failure (e.g. Figure 3(c)), whereas the remaining exhibited interlayer fracture (e.g. Figure 3(d)). Generally, fracture surfaces of the three grades of materials are remarkably similar (Figures 3(a)-(c)). This similarity forms a contrast to the quite large difference in their toughness values shown in Figure 2 (these micrographs were taken at regions immediately ahead of the pre-crack front, where the toughness was measured).

(a) Grade A (b) Grade B (c) Grade C fibre/matrix interfacial failure (d) Grade C interlayer failure

Figure 3 SEM micrographs showing fracture surfaces of mode II specimens

3.2 Investigation of Fracture Mechanisms Using CNF Test Geometry

3.2.1 Critical process zone concept and CNF test geometry

An ideal way to investigate the mechanisms involved in the fracture of the interleaved materials, which has been shown to comprise both interfacial and interlayer fracture, is to carry out fractographic examinations on samples obtained at the individual stages of the entire fracture process. Based on experiments on adhesive specimens [6] and numerical analysis of interlayered composites [7,8], it can be expected that the interlayer may probably sustain a certain extent of plastic deformation within a *critical process zone*. However, this zone cannot be secured with the ENF type of test geometry which is essentially unstable.

The authors speculated that the central notch flexural (CNF) test [9,10], devised as an alternative to the ENF mode II delamination test, promises a potential to provide the critical process zone. This is based on an observation that there exists an analogy between the symmetric configurations of the CNF test (Figure 4(a)) and the double-notch four-point-bending test (Figure 4(b)). The latter has been successfully employed in the fracture studies of bulk polymers to create and preserve a critical process zone [11]. To explore this speculation, the three grades of materials were tested in the CNF geometry with a cross-head speed of 0.5 mm/minute. In order to grasp the entire process of delamination from the start, the specimens were tested without pre-cracking.

Figure 4 Center notch flexural (CNF) and double notch three point bend (DN4PB) tests

At the beginning of this CNF attempt, specimens were loaded until unstable fracture occurred. The characteristics of the load-deflection responses were very similar to those of the ENF specimens. Visual examinations of failed specimens showed that they delaminated

Figure 5 SEM micrographs showing path of delamination (mode II, Grade C specimen)

completely at one of the delamination starter film tips, but no delamination propagation seemed to have occurred at the other tip of the film. The region surrounding this apparently non-propagated film tip was cut out, polished and examined under a microscope. Surprisingly, delamination propagation was always found over a small distance at this end as well. Therefore such a CNF test failed to create the expected critical process zone. It is interesting to note that the delamination crack started from the PTFE crack starter at the mid-thickness position of the interlayer but ended up in a ply as an intraply crack. In fact, along its path and across its width, the delamination crack experienced pure interlayer fracture, interlayer/ply interface and eventually predominant fiber/matrix interfacial fracture within the ply. Figures 5(a)-(b) are micrographs taken from the edge of one of the samples examined. Figure 5(a) shows fracture of the interlayer itself, while Figure 5(b) displays interlayer/ply interfacial failure of the same delamination crack further away from the starter film tip. Evidence of delamination propagation inside a ply at fiber/matrix interface can be found in [5].

In order to obtain a process zone, a different loading scheme was adopted in this CNF investigation. In this second type of test, loading was stopped after the onset of the nonlinearity in the load-deflection response before the peak load was reached. No delamination propagation was visible by naked eyes at either end of the delamination starter film. However, under an optical microscope, in most of the specimens, a small amount of delamination propagation was found at one end of the PTFE delamination starter and a process zone was detected at the other. Apparently, the small delamination propagation is sub-critical crack extension. Based on the observations in these two types of CNF tests, Figure 6 proposes schematically the sequence of events during such flexural type delamination fracture.

Figure 6 Schematic representation of concluded sequence of events in mode II delamination

3.2.2 Delamination initiation

Figures 7(a) and (b) are transmission optical micrographs showing the process zone in a grade C specimen. These were taken at the same position of the same specimen, but crossed polarizers were used in (b). The fact that the part of the interlayer ahead of the delamination starter is bright under the cross-polarizers indicates that there exists a zone of plastic deformation filling the entire height of the interlayer (it should be noted that away from this crack tip region, the interlayers were completely dark under cross-polarized light). Furthermore, within this zone, a narrow band of deformation is distinctively shown which may be associated with localized shear. It is noted that in grades A and B, no such obvious plastic deformation zone was detected.

3.3.3 Delamination propagation

The present fractographic examination has shown clearly the occurrence of sub-critical delamination with the present materials, the possibility of which has been argued in the literature. Matrix inelasticity and sub-critical crack growth have been proposed to be the possible mechanisms associated with the minor nonlinearity just before the unstable fracture (see Figures 1(b) and 6) typically found in mode II delamination fracture tests [3]. It is noted here that although inelastic deformation at the delamination crack tip does exist, sub-critical delamination propagation

as seen in the present samples should account for the absolute majority of the decrease in specimen stiffness which is manifested by the nonlinearity on the load-deflection response.

(a) Region near film delamination starter, white light

(b) Same as (a) but with crossed-polarizers

Figure 7 Transmission optical micrographs showing plastic deformation before delamination growth in a mode II grade C specimen (CNF test, load stopped before unstable fracture)

Examination of the completely loaded CNF specimens revealed that in material A, the propagated delamination was largely confined to its initial plane during propagation. However, in the interlayered cases, the delamination shifted from the center of the interlayer to an interlayer/ply interface and sometimes a few fibers deep inside the ply.

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

4.1 Discussion

Pre-cracking was proposed as a measure to eliminate the artificial influence on fracture energy by the resin-rich pocket ahead of the film crack starter in conventional high fiber volume fraction composites [3,4]. For materials with interlayers thicker than this film starter, pre-cracking may not serve the purpose of promoting consistent fracture energy data clearly associated with a certain micro-mechanism. In light of the evidence gathered in this work that delamination fracture assumes a complex path in which fracture mechanisms are not consistent, the authors would recommend that interlayered specimens not be pre-cracked but instead be fractured in a stable delamination propagation test to establish the fracture energy as a function of delamination path with mechanisms clearly identified along this path. Work following this line is under way at the time of this writing. One point worth mentioning is that the pre-cracking in the ENF test reported in section 2.2 left the delamination front at an uncertain position and therefore the energy data cannot be rigorously attributed to a definite mechanism.

The plastic deformation zone shown in Figure 7 indicates that even under the constraint of its two adjacent plies, the interlayer is still capable of deforming plastically nearly throughout its thickness. This zone of deformation stretched over a distance several times of its thickness. Obviously, such a zone would contribute considerably to energy absorption during the fracture. It would be interesting to carry out similar examination to investigate the deformation of an interlayer when the initial crack is located at the lower or upper interlayer/ply interface instead of its center. This process zone examination technique using the CNF configuration may also be applied to experimental investigations for assessing the dependence of fracture energy on the thickness of the interlayer.

4.2 Conclusions

From pre-cracked test specimens, mode I and II delamination fracture energies were found to increase with the extent of interlayering in the three BMI systems. These correspond to improvements in the CAI strength. Fractographic studies on mode II fracture specimens showed that delamination propagated within its original plane in non-interlayered material A. However, it propagated through a complex path involving multiple fracture mechanisms in materials B and C. The sequence of fracture events in interlayered materials in ENF and CNF tests has been deduced as 1) the formation of plastic deformation zone ahead of delamination starter, 2) sub-critical delamination growth, and 3) unstable propagation. The zone of the plastic deformation has been found to spread nearly throughout the thickness of the 30 μm interlayer in material C.

It is further concluded that to accurately understand the fracture energy absorption behavior of relatively thick interlayered materials, delamination fracture should be investigated using a stable propagation test with no pre-cracking.

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